

More on the crab spider *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi* Lessert, 1933 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The crab spider *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi* Lessert, 1933 was described from Umbilo in KwaZulu-Natal but has been recorded throughout South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described based on photographs of live specimens. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

A large number of Thomisidae have been sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and based on the description and drawings of Lessert (1933), *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi* was recognised as one of the sampled thomisid species. The species was described from Umbilo in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *Phrynarachne* Thorell, 1869 is represented by 35 species and 10 of the species are known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

The only data on the species is the original description of the male and female in 1933. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on live specimens with notes on their behaviour, conservation, and distribution in South Africa.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Requests were also made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum and several photographs of *P. melloleitaoi* from several localities throughout South Africa have been received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Phrynarachne melloleitaoi Lessert, 1933

Phrynarachne melloleitaoi Lessert, 1933: 121; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014: 246.

Diagnostic characteristics: *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi* is recognised by the integument that is hard, unequal, grooved, and the abdomen bearing distinct tubercles; The abdomen shape and colour are variable and Lessert (1933) provided drawings of the abdomen of both the male and female. The abdomen is mottled yellow-brown to dark brown (Figs. 1–3); rugose, with two strong abdominal tubercles directed slightly upwards; shape of tubercles variable from almost smooth in a V-shape (Fig. 1) to very rugose with numerous tubercles (Figs 8, 12); some specimens with two white spots midway on abdomen (Fig. 1). The body and legs are covered by short, white, club-shaped setae frequently arranged in rows (Fig. 11). Carapace with eye region narrow anteriorly; two equally recurved eye rows; anterior row narrower than posterior row; median eyes half the size of the lateral eyes; lateral eyes raised on common tubercles. Legs dark brown, mottled, front legs longer, thicker and more robust than hind legs; with very strong paired setae (Figs 9). Female and male almost same size, males only slightly smaller and darker: total length 4–6 mm.

Figures 1–3. *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi*: 1. Male from Wakefield Farm. 2. Female from Camps Bay. 3. Female from Cloverly, Cape Town. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–8. *Phrynarachne melloleitai*: 4. Male abdomen. 5–8. Drawings of male abdomen and palp and female abdomen after Lessert, 1933).

Figures 9–12. *Phrynarachne melloleitai*: 9. Macrosetae leg I. 10. Epigyne. 11. Setae on carapace. 12. Female from Addo National Park. Photo credits: 9–11 A. Dippenaar-Schoeman; 12. Linda Wiese.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Lesotho, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Cwebbe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Kasouga, 16 km WSW of Port Alfred (-33.63, 26.43); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Mazepa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Zuurberg Pass (-33.32, 25.68); Addo Elephant NP, Woody Cape (-33.57, 25.68); Burg Lengeling, 15 km SE on R67 to Port Alfred (-33.32, 26.67); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.206, 24.708). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.62); Wakefield farm (-29.26, 29.56); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Karkloof (-29.301, 30.21). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Northern Cape:** Vanderkloof Dam Orange River (-29.99, 24.74). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Bloubergstrand (-33.77, 18.45); Delvera Stellenbosch (-33.833, 18.857); Robben Island (-33.8, 18.35). Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37).

Known distribution in South Africa

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant dwellers and many of the specimens were sampled from trees. Specimens were sampled while beating and sweep netting the vegetation in the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Haddad *et al.*, 2013, Foord *et al.*, 2011). The species has also been sampled from citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). Adults were sampled throughout the year, and juveniles were sampled from May until October.

Members of *Phrynarachne* are known as bird-dropping crab spiders as some species make a disc of white silk on the surface of leaves on which they position themselves, resulting in a striking resemblance to the excrement of birds. However, this behaviour has not been observed in *P. melloleitoai*.

CONSERVATION

There are no known threats and no conservation actions are recommended. The species is protected in several reserves and parks such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020), Cwebe Nature Reserve, Loteni Nature Reserve, Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve, Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009).

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